

Impact of Negative News on Ethical Fashion: Case Study to Investigate the Effect of Fashion CSR Ad Framing on Purchase Intention

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Abstract—The purpose of this paper is to examine the relationship between the fashion corporate social responsibility (CSR) ad framing and consumer purchase behaviours with the focus on consumer's concern and involvement towards fashion brands. A self-completion questionnaire was administered to 200 respondents. Factor analysis and other statistical analyses were applied to test hypotheses. The results suggested that the quality of the product was the most important factor when consumers purchase fashion brand products with high level of responsibility towards unethical practices but surprisingly favourability for fast fashion. Unexpectedly, it was shown that consumers took the plenty of blame, but not much responsibility on buying fast fashion evading their responsibility to CSR ad, and their purchase intentions remained unchanged. The result, on the other hand, showed that fashion CSR ads can significantly moderate individuals' emotions even though this had no significant correlation with the purchase intentions. Despite the limited sample size and geographical region, this research has important implications for contemporary fashion brands that use ad framing to understand how consumers' involvement and concernedness toward the CSR actions in ad, influence their favourability (purchase intention) for fashion brands.

Keywords—Framing effect, CSR advertisements, consumer behaviour, purchase intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

TODAY, consumers are surrounded by numerous advertisement framings which improve public's perception of firms and the effectiveness of advertising has been considered by previous researches [1]. Many researchers argue that advertisers need to pay close attention to perceived consumers' perceptions of advertising in relation to ad framing effects [2], [3]. For example, framed information may play a significant role in consumers' decision making when they estimate the products in details [4]. The types of framed messages are divided into positive and negative tone. A positively framed message is inclined to emphasise on potential gain to consumers by using the brand. On the contrary, a negatively framed message highlights the need of choosing the brand to prevent potential losses. Previous studies suggested that positive tone of frames is more favourable to us since it encourages desirable responses than negatively framed messages [5]. Evidence also showed that the impact of message

framing can be communicated differently by different conditions. For example, a study suggested that consumers' perception of performance risk is likely to be higher when the negative message is shown [6]. The impact of advertising framing has become one of the salient factors in consumers' intentions towards brands' products and researchers began to investigate the moderating variables of attitudes. Reference [7] suggested that the effect of framed advertising provide different consequences, depending on how products in ad are framed. The first main objective of this study is to explore the relationship between framing effect and cognitive biases associated with purchase intention. According to [8], people's conclusion can vary when using different formats of same option. Particularly, decision making in social setting has a great effect on the interaction between emotion and reasoning in which emotion and social motivation compete each other [9]. For example, perceived susceptibility and risk behaviours form "blame behaviour", because these entail the possibility of risk and one may be a bad luck. Theoretically, [10] investigated the effect of moral responsibility in resultant luck which pointed out the problem of moral luck of legal theory. For example, with moral theory in [1], when misfortune or fortune happens to us, we are likely to assign either blame or praise for our actions and its outcomes even though they are not directly related with the consequences or actions. Therefore, this study will investigate the impact of negatively framed messages and images on consumer's purchase intention in relation to a responsibility on social issues.

It is important for fashion corporates to understand and devise some ways to prompt consumers' opinions and feelings in the most effective way to gain greater involvement and favourability toward their brands. Previous study [11] suggested that the stockholders with high and low CSR involvement play a significant role in communication needs, with motivated information processing (peripheral vs. central route). It was suggested that the emotional advertising requires less information and resources but it is more likely to appeal to consumers' emotions followed by peripheral routes while informative promotions tend to require cognitive processing capacities (central route). However, the correlation between perceived risk, involvement and incongruent framing to require higher cognitive effort has not been suggested. According to [12], incongruent information gain peoples' attention, higher recall and positive evaluation and thus CSR ads are often utilised in the fashion industry. Two models of persuasion were produced; heuristic-systematic model (HSM) [13] and

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elaboration likelihood model (ELM) [14]. ELM and HSM generate differing persuasion outcomes and levels of cognitive effort, which greatly affect consumers' long-term attitude towards products. However, they suggested that effortful and careful thinking only operate when people are motivated to process it systematically, otherwise, attitude change will be described under less meaningful. In sum, even when one attempted to hold the risk framing hypothesis with ELM, it is not clear that if gain framed information are more likely to make people to be risk-aversion and low motivation while loss framed information produces high perceived vulnerability to take a low risk option [15], [16]. Therefore, this study will take another critical look at the hypothesis that perceived risk (concern) moderates incongruent framed information (fashion brand's CSR ads) by investigating the relationship between the level of involvement and concern about the social issues in ad and favourability toward brands. It could be hypothesized that CSR ad will lead to high concernedness, and this in turn increases consumers' motivation and product involvement to certain products (favourability). Finally, it was previously shown that the gain- message framing leads to positive feelings (favourability) and a higher risk aversion (low involvement), while loss-message framing leads to negative feelings (concerns) and low risk aversion (high involvement) [7], [17]. However, previous studies have not indeed found support for these expectation, and other studies have found only partial support. Therefore, this study will investigate the role of incongruent framing (fashion CSR ad) by understanding correlation between concerns, involvement and favourability.

II. HYPOTHESES

This study consisted of three main hypotheses.

- H1 – Negatively framed advertising messages (loss messages) in negative image show lower favourability than positively framed message.
- H2 – CSR ad will lead to high concernedness, and in turn increases consumer's involvement and favourability.
- H3 – Incongruent advertising framings (CSR ads) can moderate individuals' emotions (fear and involvement) and favourability (product involvement).

III. METHODS

A. Participants and Design

Participants were recruited in two different cities in the UK; Oxford and Southampton. Female students, aged 18 to 25, have participated in the study and were given face-face questionnaire. Female are far more likely to be persuaded by message framing than men [18]. Young people, in particular, tend to respond more to bad events in order to perform human responsibilities and would like to give punishment by their purchasing decisions [19], [20]. Therefore, the survey had recruited female students to gain insight into their previous experiences of the brand. The questionnaire consisted of three parts. The first part was to investigate the effect of negatively message framing. The second part was to assess the self-responsibility toward negative news. Finally, the last part of the

questionnaire was to test the effect of CSR in relation to consumers' concern and involvement. Before proceeding to the main questions, participants were asked about their importance towards the brand when they purchase products in order to understand consumers' attitude and purchase intention by ranking the 4 items; price, quality, service and brand name. In addition to this, they also rated 5-point Likert scale to measure their attitudes towards fast-fashion brands and responsibility which are involved in negative information.

B. Pilot Study and Statistics

For validity of the scales, message framing was checked by conducting a pre-test based on the 10 participant's feedbacks before the main experiment. The pilot test data were analyzed using the reliability test (Cronbach's α), correlation analysis and a regression test (Table I) to ensure the high internal reliability and consistency. All data from 200 respondents were collected and analyzed using SPSS statistics 23.0. Frequency analysis, T-test, Correlation analysis and regression analysis were conducted for the hypotheses testing.

TABLE I
RELIABILITY ANALYSIS

Source	Cronbach's α
Favorability (pre)	.726
Favorability (post)	.764
Responsibility	.787
Concern towards information	.634
Involvement towards information	.676
Favorability towards the brand	.659

C. Hypothesis 1 (H1)

The participants were randomly assigned to one of two conditions in a design (negative and positive message framing). Reliability of the data obtained was consistent with that reported by [21]. For H1, two different types of CSR ads were used; one with positive message and the other with negative message as shown in Figs. 1 (a) and (b). To minimize confounding effects from using different imageries, same negative image was used for ads with different frames. Two different participant groups were exposed to different fictitious framed CSR advertising messages in negative image. Participants were randomly assigned and instructed to rate it by answering the 5 Likert scales before and after viewing the ad, which assess brand favourability and attitudes. Existing attitudes on fashion brand "Zara" were rated by participants using the 5-point Likert scale before viewing the ad [22], [23]. The five items were positive-negative, like-dislike, pleasant-unpleasant and good-bad as well as the quality of the company's products (poor-high quality) were measured [24]. In the second phase, participants then were instructed to view the fictitious ad, and complete next part which consisted of a 10 item, 5-point scale to measure the willingness of long-term usage and loyalty toward the brand based on a scale from unfavorable to favorable [25]. The 10 item constructs include brand loyalty, purchase intention, brand awareness and perceived quality to present strongly disagree or strongly agree [26].

(a) (b)

Fig. 1 Two different types of CSR ads; positive message (a) and negative message (b)

D. Hypothesis 2 (H2)

The participants were asked to rate the level of agreement or disagreement between the social responsibility of companies and their own using a 5-point Likert scale, adopted from [27]-[29]. Participants were given four different events of the fashion brands which contained the failure of CSR and strategic CSR concept (negative information). For processing this test, four different types of company's unethical practice were conducted; one with environmental pollution issue followed by others including animal skin bag, cheap labour and corporate crime. Participants was instructed to rate their level of responsibility after reading each corporates' negative issues. They read "If I buy clothes from a company that does something wrong, I am responsible for society in general?", "If I purchase crocodile leather bag (they are cut while alive), I am not animal conservationists?", "If you buy clothes which made by unsustainable materials, my choice could not be based on environmental behaviours" and "If I buy brand which use cheap labour, I am partly responsible for their abuse" using a 4 items summated Likert scales ranging from 1 (strongly agree) to 5 (strongly disagree).

E. Hypothesis 3 (H3)

Participants were exposed to two different framed CSR advertising (gain and loss message and positive and negative images) with the use of two different events. First CSR advertising depicted dead bodies of factory workers wrapped in the plastic bag with other survivors around them (this was an image from the real event in Bangladesh in 2013) and the slogan written as "It is our responsibility" in terms of human rights and labour standards (Fig. 2 (a)). Second CSR ad contained one model wearing environmental friendly product and expressed supporting environment by declaring slogan as "Go green, wearing blue" to support less chemical and pure fashion (Fig. 2 (b)). After viewing two ads, participants were instructed to rate each three favorability, involvement and concern. They were then instructed to read the questionnaire which contained three categories to measure favorability, responsibility, concerns and involvement toward CSR advertisings and brands. After reading the ads, they rated ads with their thoughts in terms of brands with use of Likert scales. To assess the effectiveness of manipulations, each dependent measure was assessed by putting nonstandard questions in mix. For analysis of the data, a composite score (numerical average of the scales) was used for each of the dependent measures.

(a) (b)

Fig. 2 Two different framed CSR ads

F. Ethics Statement

All participants are provided with participation information sheet and informed consent form. The study was conducted in accordance with the ethical guidelines and ethical standards (ERGO number 26887).

IV. RESULTS

A. H1 – Negatively Framed Advertising Messages (Loss Messages) in Negative Image Show Lower Favourability than Positively Framed Message

Many companies invested significant time and effort to improve their advertising to communicate with consumers. To capture consumers' attention, fashion advertisers use framing using different forms of messages and images. However, consumers' responses are often unpredictable and vary depending on different framing. Study 1 proposed that the consumers, who viewed a negatively framed advertising message in the negative image, show lower favourability than who were presented with a positively framed advertising message in the identical negative image. It was found that the group with a negatively framed advertising message had shown a lower favourability toward the brand after viewing the advertising. Table II shows that both groups had similar mean values with standard deviations (SD) for pre-favourability. However, the group with negative message showed greater decrease in mean values compared to the positive group ($M_{\text{positive}}=3.27, SD=0.49$ vs $M_{\text{negative}}=3.19, SD=0.49$). Although the p value was calculated to be 0.264 and therefore, the interaction between message frame and favourability was not considered to be statistically significant (hence rejection of H1), this difference could have become statistically significant ($p=0.046$) if there were more participants (total=600, 300 for each framing). Overall, the different framing of adverts led to differences in the favourability based on viewing of negatively framed message or positively framed messages with the identical negative image but the difference was not significant.

TABLE II
EFFECT OF DIFFERENT FRAMED MESSAGES ON FAVORABILITY

	Group	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.
favorability(pre)	positive	3.44	.66	.043	.966
	negative	3.45	.64		
favorability(post)	positive	3.27	.49	1.121	.264
	negative	3.19	.49		

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001
(Positive message N=100 and Negative message N=100)

B. Study 2 (H2) – CSR Ad Leads to High Concernedness and in Turn Increases Consumer’s Involvement and Favourability

CSR has become one of the crucial components to enhance overall companies’ reputation in cynical business world. Healthy corporate actions strongly affect consumers’ buying decision in which consumers are inclined to make an ethical choice, and this in turn would result in greater profits. Although many consumers urge companies to be more socially responsible and create their products in more ethical way, consumers are not often willing to take responsibility from their choice of brands when they are aware of possible companies’ wrongdoing. Therefore, the hypothesis was tested to measure how individuals’ negative feelings toward negative information influence purchase intention (favourability) towards the brand. Unexpectedly, it was shown that consumers were not very responsible as they were not willing to associate bad CSR with their purchasing intention (Mean=2.74, SD=0.57) as shown in Table III. The participants showed the highest level of responsibility on question 3 with mean of 2.81 and the lowest responsibility when they were asked about the question 4 with mean of 2.65. This demonstrates that the consumers feel more responsible for the environment issues than the issues such as cheap labour. However, H2 is rejected which means the consumers are likely to evade their responsibility to CSR ad and their purchase intentions remain unchanged.

TABLE III
RESPONSIBILITY TOWARDS DECISIONS OF PURCHASING THE PRODUCT

Items		n	%	M	SD
1. When I buy clothes from a company that does something wrong, I am partly responsible for their wrong-doing?	Strongly Disagree	13	6.5	2.75	0.94
	Disagree	74	37		
	Neither	71	35.5		
	Agree	35	17.5		
	Strongly Agree	7	3.5		
2. When I purchase bags from a brand that use crocodile leather, I am not animal conservationists?	Strongly Disagree	20	10	2.77	0.99
	Disagree	57	28.5		
	Neither	81	40.5		
	Agree	33	16.5		
	Strongly Agree	9	4.5		
3. If you keep up with latest fashion trend by spending on a specific brand made by unsustainable materials such as synthetic polymers, my choice could be not based on environmental behaviour?	Strongly Disagree	10	5	2.81	0.93
	Disagree	72	36		
	Neither	70	35		
	Agree	42	21		
	Strongly Agree	6	3		
4. If you buy brand which is more cheaply available by using cheap labour, I am partly responsible for their abuse?	Strongly Disagree	20	10	2.65	0.97
	Disagree	76	38		
	Neither	64	32		
	Agree	35	17.5		
	Strongly Agree	5	2.5		
Total		200		2.74	.57

C. Study 3 (H3) Incongruent Advertising Framings (CSR Ads) Can Moderate Individuals’ Emotions (Concern and Involvement) and Favourability (Purchase Intention)

CSR from companies is a significant factor to determine the brand image and serves as a key for communication and expresses the character of a firm such as organisations’ values

and behavioural expectation. Therefore, some fashion companies express their responsibility for ethical issues by using effective framing through advertising rather than featuring their products.

TABLE IV
COMPARISON BETWEEN INVOLVEMENT AND CONCERN TOWARDS THE INFORMATION IN AD

	Mean	SD	t	p
Involvement towards information in ad	3.42	0.67	2.089*	.038
Concern towards information in ad	3.31	0.70		

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001, N=200

TABLE V
CORRELATIONS BETWEEN INVOLVEMENT AND CONCERN TOWARDS THE INFORMATION IN AD AND FAVOURABILITY TOWARD THE BRAND

	Favourability towards the brand	Involvement toward information in ad	Concern toward information in ad
Favourability towards the brand	r = 1		
Involvement towards information in ad	r = -.116	r = 1	
Concern towards information in ad	r = .000	r = .356***	r = 1

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

TABLE VI
EFFECT OF INDIVIDUAL EMOTIONS (INVOLVEMENT AND CONCERN) FROM ADS ON FAVOURABILITY

	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta				Tolerance	VIF
Constant	3.831	.572			6.698	.000		
Involvement towards the information in ad	-.337	.191	-.133		-1.761	.080	.874	1.145
Concern towards the information in ad	.114	.183	.047		.625	.533	.874	1.145

R Square=.016, Adjusted R Square=.006, F=1.551

* p<.05, ** p<.01, *** p<.001

According to [30], many businesses employ good CSR strategies to distinguish themselves as the best company from the other competitors. However, socially responsible advertisement may increase people’s concerns or repulsion rather than involvement towards the issue in ad. The hypothesis was tested to measure people’s level of involvement and concernedness toward the CSR actions in ad and how they can influence favourability (purchase intention). It was found that participants generally showed high level of concern (mean 3.31, SD 0.70) and involvement (mean 3.42, SD 0.67) towards the information in ad (Table IV). There was also higher degree of involvement than concern and this difference was significant (p=0.038). Therefore, this indicates that the consumers are more positive towards the ad as they were more likely to participate in issues rather than worrying about the issues. However, from the correlation analysis, it was found that there was a negative correlation between the involvement towards

the ad and favourability towards the brand ($r = -.0116$), although this was not statistically significant. There was no correlation between the concern and the favourability ($r = 0$). These data suggest that there are no significant interaction between individual's emotions (involvement and concern) towards the ad and favourability towards the brand (Table V). Further analysis also showed similar results; both involvement ($\beta = -.133, p = 0.080$) and concern ($\beta = .047, p = 0.533$) towards the ad were found to be not statistically significant. On the other hand, the involvement towards the ad was shown to decrease in the favourability. Therefore, it can be concluded that H3 may be partially supported as Fashion CSR ads can moderate individuals' emotions but there was no significant correlation between the emotions and purchase intention. The consumers who experienced increased involvement towards the information after viewing the ad showed decreased favourability, although neither of these was statistically significant.

D. Importance towards the Brand

TABLE VII
 IMPORTANCE TOWARDS THE BRAND

	Frequency	Per cent
Price	37	18.5
Quality	142	71
Service	6	3
Brand name	15	7.5
Total	200	100

TABLE VIII
 IMPORTANCE TOWARDS THE BRAND

		M	S. D	M \pm S.D
Brand name	1. Brand name is not important to me when I am deciding on which product to buy	2.58	1.07	3.04 \pm .73
	2. I rely heavily on brand name when shopping	2.78	1.01	
	3. I trust reputable brands more than lesser-known brand	3.51	.90	
Favorability towards fast fashion	4. Most brands are generally similar in quality	3.11	.98	3.04 \pm .48
	5. Fast fashion brands are of comparable quality to luxury brand	3.13	.96	
	6. It is risky to buy fast brands	3.02	.98	
	7. Fast brands are cheaper than luxury brands due to different services	2.56	.92	
Quality	8. The quality of the product is important me than price when shopping.	4.02	.82	
Price	9. It is important to me the product is reasonably priced	3.96	.79	
Review	10. I will stop buying my favorite product after reading bad online reviews.	3.24	1.03	
Responsibility	11. I believe if I purchasing brands which are involved in bad practices, it is my responsibility	3.38	.84	

Prior to completing the survey, participants were asked about their opinions towards the brand when they purchase products to understand consumers' attitude and purchase intention by ranking the 4 items such as price, quality, service and brand name as well as 5-point Likert scale. In addition to this, the attitudes towards fast-fashion brands and responsibility were also measured. The results indicated that the quality of the

product was the most important (71%) followed by the price (18.5%). The values for the brand name and service stood at 7.5% and 3% respectively. Consistently, the means indicated that the quality is most important when purchasing fashion products (Mean=4.02, SD=0.82), followed by price (Mean=3.96, SD=0.79), review (Mean=3.24, SD=1.03) brand name (Mean=3.04, SD=0.73) as shown in Table VIII. In addition, this result also shows the participants' thoughts in terms of importance of responsibility toward their purchasing practices and fast fashion. The results suggested that consumers' favourability toward the fast fashion is positive (Mean=3.04, SD=0.48) as some participants considered that most brands are similar in quality as well as fashion brand. The high level of responsibility (Mean=3.38, SD=0.84) was shown when they were asked their purchasing intention towards brands which are involved in bad practices.

V. DISCUSSION

This study provides insight into today's dynamic communication platform in which consumers are surrounded by numerous messages which positively influence consumers' purchasing intention. Previous studies pointed out that different types of communicative messages create individual views on firms [31]. Therefore, well-written structures and communication should be considered for effective management. However, the results in this study indicated that framing had no significant indirect effect on intentions and attitudes since the framing bias operates decision making procedures [32]. Therefore, the framework from looking at how message framing will be most effective suggests that they must engage in consideration of how the message frame relates to the individuals' emotional engagement and how the contents of a message may influence different emotions through moderating variables. Across these studies, consumers' attitudes towards the brand choices were briefly outlined for predicting framing effects. This study looked at the message framing, message contents and recipient effects with the use of comprehensive framework and the approach was adopted from other perspective principles between individual and situation variables [33]-[34]. Study 1 demonstrated that negatively framed advertising messages (loss messages) in negative image show lower favourability than positively framed message, although the difference was not significant. Study 2 provided evidence that individuals' negative feeling from negative information does not negatively affect favourability towards the brand due to evasion of responsibility. Study 3 demonstrated effect of fashion brand; CSR ads using negative issues showed no significant correlation between the emotions (concern vs. involvement) and favourability despite some evidences of decrease in favourability was seen due to the involvement towards the ad.

First, one of the most influential notions in message framing holds that positively framed advertising messages (gain messages) is more persuasive and increase purchasing intention, whereas negatively framed advertising messages (loss messages) results in less favourability. However, the results from study 1 did not agree with previous results in the

literature. This could be due to the limited number of participants (n=200) and a relatively small difference in favourability between two types of framing. This could also be explained by boomerang effect [35] which suggests that people are likely to associate with issues by maintaining their initial opinions or change their opinions entirely to the opposite side under pressure and this is more likely in young people. Participants in this study were relatively young. Therefore, the assumption is that some participants may have failed to use cognitive processing capacities which generated higher level of attention and interpretability to avoid negative feeling from negative framed advertising. Although, no significant difference was found between positively framed and negatively framed messages, people were less favorable towards the brand after viewing the negatively framed advertising message. Theoretically, the effect of visual image framing and picture superiority effect can be explained by [36]-[38]. The evidence showed that people are far more likely to focus on images than words, because the messages take longer time to process than pictures. In addition, negative images tend to produce negative feelings and proactive behaviors since people are habituated to seeing overall image rather than focusing on information. Because pictures have a faster access to the semantic code than word [39], the participants may bias their responses for interpreting the message framing. Therefore, the results suggested that consumers are not clearly reactive to framed message in advertising setting when they are under other variables which influence attitudes.

The result from study 2 suggested that people showed less responsibility over the negative information which did not affect their favourability towards the brand. This finding is in line with previous empirical studies concerning the correlation between negative information, moral responsibility and purchasing intention [27]-[29]. The result from study 2 did not mirror the general findings in others consumer studies. This can be theoretically explained by blame behaviour [1]; people are likely to have responsibilities towards misjudgements only when the outcomes are directly related to their controls since people are unable to justly blame and praise for their decisions when the matters are beyond their controls. Further research should address the blame behavior in more depth to understand the relationship between the avoidance system and individuals' emotion towards purchasing intention.

Lastly, for the fashion CSR ad framing condition, it was predicted that CSR ads moderate individuals' emotions and influence favourability towards the brand. Thus, fashion CSR ads would produce a concernedness which might increase the favourability towards the brand. Study 3 showed that despite significant increase in the concern and involvement towards the ad, this did not significantly influence the favourability towards the brand. One explanation could be that the promoting fashion brand through recommending ethical social practices may distract participants' interpretability which may lead to ambiguous result. Reference [40] suggested that incongruent information can lead to higher level of attention and recall; however, it shows slow processing of information. Another possible explanation for unexpected level of favourability from

both feeling of involvement and concern is that the initial perceived brand image may have influenced the processing of information. For example, previous empirical studies suggested that previous perceived brand image plays a significant role in evaluation of CSR information [41]. In sum, initial negative brand image might have decreased the motivation to engage in CSR information for some participants in which a low level of cognitive effort was required by use of peripheral routes. Alternatively, the result also can be explained by studies of resistance to persuasion [42]. From their studies, people experience feeling of avulsion when individuals are exposed to some threats in which a state of motivational arousal decreases to restore their threatened or lost freedom. Therefore, the assumption is that people might have experienced psychological reactance when they are shown CSR ads which include problematic issues which led them to higher concernedness or involvement during the study. Lastly, people's responses towards CSR ads may have been varied due to different types of CSR strategies which have impact on individuals' perceived brand images. As a result, the assumption is that some participants may have been interrupted to precisely determine their attitudes towards the brand due to increased biases towards CSR motive in ad.

Affect-priming mechanism theory by [43] suggested that advertising may influence individuals' emotions, and this in turn influences people's reactions towards the framed information. For instance, [44] argued that when people are in a negative mood, they are more likely to care about the given information due to increased motivation from concernedness. Known as the mood theory [45], [46], this suggested that people are likely to engage in self-regulation of moods, thus individuals attempt to repair their negative feeling back to positive one rather than enduring the feeling. Hence, while social responsible information in ad promotes ethical practice using problematic issues and increase concern to the viewer, framed information may be latched onto by viewers. This view was supported by the concernedness result where the people felt strong emotions over the social issues when they viewed the CSR ads without involvement. This provides insight into framing effect on emotions is supported by [47] in his examination of the correlation between the consumers and marketing discipline. He suggested that framing effect can be moderated within individuals' differences. The finding also extends the results from [48] which examined the effect of emotions on message framing and the impact of threat to the individual. Reference [49] suggested that people are indifferent to negative information only when it is considered to be insignificant since people are more attentive to advertisements when the information are perceived as the real loss which affect them. In addition, people are less receptive to the loss when they are in negative mood, because previous depressed feelings make people not to perceive the loss [50]. This view is supported by the results in correlation between feeling of concern and favourability where people with higher concern did not show proactive attitudes towards the brand.

The results in study 3 indicated that although CSR ads did not demonstrate significant correlation between the emotions

and attitudes toward the brand, people showed their willingness of involvement towards the problematic issues in CSR ad than worrying about the issues. However, feeling of involvement did not generate the higher favourability toward the brand and decrease the purchasing intention. This finding is in line with other recent findings concerning the relationship between purchasing intention and involvement. It was previously found in a consumer survey that people who are in higher involvement in event were more sceptical in terms of sustainable CSR. In sum, from study 3, the result was not significant, however, produced the importance of understanding individual variable effects such as processes of persuasion and information processing perspective of cognitive [51], which can be paid closer attention for further research.

VI. CONCLUSION

CSR framing effects have been investigated in combination with image, content and individuals' emotions. The study proposed the hypotheses based on the notion that effectiveness framing may increase the consumers' purchasing intention. The data provided partial support for the idea regarding downstream effect of negative framing on favourability and in terms of negative impact of involvement towards CSR ad on favourability. More findings for negative feelings from negative information suggested the existence of human nature such as evasion of responsibility for that purchasing intention. All these results point towards the need for consistent research aimed at better understanding of the role of fashion CSR ad and ad framing on persuasion in relation to affective state. This study has number of inherent limitations. First, university aged consumers are important portion for investigation in terms of fast-fashion and media advertising [52]. However, this study was derived from student sample which restricts the results from being generalized to other populations such as elderly. Although such samples are rampant in consumer study, it still cannot be claimed that students are representative of the general public, which decreases external validity [53], [54]. Second, it has specifically focused on students from Oxford and Southampton as a single response platform. Future research should expand the perspectives, testing wider sample such as other countries, ages and gender by widening the frame of reference of this study. Likewise, it can be addressed with high users in fashion industry, such as fashion blogger, models and fashion students. Therefore, it could be also suggested to ensure the framing phrases which may vary recipients' responses. For instance, young people may respond more favorably towards practicality and productivity phrase as the quality was the most significant one, which was revealed from this study, while fashionable people are likely to be favorable towards other factors. In addition, avenues for future research include studying the effect of emotional context. As such, this study invites further investigation of consumers' cognitive processes and self-persuasion process which raises a number of interesting questions that have not yet been addressed in existing academic studies. For instance, "does the ability to engage in information moderate cognitive processes when a person an experience feeling of avulsion towards a certain issue

in ad?" "Is a negative emotional component present that may interact with individuals' motivation regarding perceived brand image?" "Do fashion CSR advertising initiatives types such as proactive and reactive differentiate consumers' reaction to framing message?". It is hoped that these questions will be addressed in future study and lead to more discussion and research in the area.

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